

SERVICE DELIVERY CAPABILITIES AND STUDENTS' SATISFACTION IN PRIVATELY-OWNED UNIVERSITIES IN F.C.T. ABUJA.

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Department of Business Management & Marketing, Baze University, Abuja. Nigeria.

Department of Entrepreneurship, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

jude.madu@bazeuniversity.edu.ng/Judemadu71@gmail.com/amalaw2004@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12206018>

Keywords:

Customer satisfaction, Service delivery, Employee's engagement, Service culture, Service Quality, Customer's Experience, Service Responsiveness.

Abstract: Private universities in FCT Abuja are saddled with the problems of weak students' enrollment and competition. This has resulted to weak cash inflow and profit. The aim of this study is to examine how Service Delivery Capabilities measured through service culture, employee's engagement, service quality and service responsiveness relate with Students satisfaction in privately-owned Universities in F.C, T, Abuja. To realize these objectives, the response of a sample size of 383 respondents statistically selected from a population of 9130 students of three privately-owned universities in FCT Abuja was obtained through a Questionnaire. Data obtained was analyzed with Descriptive statistics, while the Hypotheses postulated were tested with the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Major findings show that service culture, employees' engagement, service quality and service responsiveness relate with students' satisfaction at different levels. Based on these findings, the study recommends: a reduction in the process for delivering services; prompt response to students' complaints; constant contact with students and their parents so as to ascertain their level of satisfaction at all times; utilize technologically-advanced teaching aids in good learning environment; and utilize skilled staff. This study contributes to existing knowledge by explaining how service delivery tools can be applied to improve the patronage and profitability to privately-owned universities.

Background of the study

The major apparatus to human development is Education, since the development of every society or nation is achieved through human, it

therefore implies that education is the key to growth and development of every State, Country, Nation, Society and the world at large (Olawore, 2017). The University Education is

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

where the needed skills for the development of societies are acquired. The Primary and Secondary levels of education are principally aimed at preparing man's intellectual ability to grasp the skills that would be inculcated at the university level (Ekpoh, 2018).

At the eve of Nigerian's independence in 1960, University education was a luxury achievable by very few children from patrician families, and another few that were influenced by the proponents of religion and religious activities in the country then. The need for educated manpower after the independence spurred many to seek for University Education. The first known tertiary institution in Nigeria was the university college Ibadan which was an affiliate of the University of London. Before it was fully commissioned into a fully fledged university in 1962, the University of Nigeria Nsukka was established in 1960

(Hoque et.al,2018). Then followed other premier universities by the Regional Governments, and later Federal universities, State universities and privately-owned universities. As at December 2020 there were 170 universities duly licensed by the National Universities Commission and operating (NUC, 2020). These universities were made up of 43 Federal universities, 48 State universities and 79 privately-owned universities and more than one hundred applications are currently awaiting recommendation by the National University Commission for final approval by the Federal Executive Council, thereby increasing the level

of competition among privately-owned universities in Nigeria. Unfortunately, deteriorating security situations in government owned universities in Nigeria mostly, and prevalence of pandemic in foreign countries have encourage students and their parents to relocate to Nigeria (Madu, 2016). This has encouraged an increase in the number of students seeking admission into privately-owned universities in Nigeria, thereby attracting more and severe competitors to the industry. Privately-owned universities in Nigeria (mostly owned by private individuals and religious organizations) do not receive funding or any other form of support from the governments. Yet they must survive so as to realize their aims and objectives. The major source of survival for every organization is consistent and loyal patronage from customers (Wohlstetter et.al., 2004). In the privately-owned university industry in Nigeria, the students are the major customers. Their satisfaction retains their continuous patronage to the university of their choice, and their testimonies attract enrollment from others seeking for admission. Steady and increased enrollment by students at all levels is a boast to the profitability of the privately-owned university. To realize students' satisfaction, the university must have efficient and effective service delivery capabilities. Therefore, how to attract students' satisfaction through service delivery capabilities by privately-owned universities is the crux of this study.

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

Statement of the Problem

Given the number of privately-owned universities and the difficult economic situation in present day Nigeria, there is competition among privately-owned universities in the country. The privately-owned universities are suffering from weak student's enrollment which is responsible for their inability to remunerate their staff and adequately fund other necessities of their institution (Olawure, 2017). The situation is so sad to the extent that some of the universities have started pruning the number of facilities and departments they had earlier obtained accreditation for, many of their staff are sacked indiscriminately, thereby worsening the economic development of the country. To improve students enrollment, the privately-owned universities have tried out some measures such as enhancing on promotional activities, award of Honorary Ph.D degrees to wealthy individuals, requesting for donations and financial assistance from church members and wealthy individuals and reduction in fees, yet the dwindling students enrollments persist (Ekpoh, 2018). This therefore gives the need to apply the concept of service delivery capabilities. According to Teya, 2011, one major strategy to attract customer patronage in the services industry such as education is excellent service delivery system and management. In a competitive environment, the major determinant of profitable business is the services delivery management model and the ability to execute it (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000).

This requires the service organization to create value and deliver such value to ultimate consumers. The components of services delivery capabilities include: Service culture, Employee engagements, services quality and customer experience (Ankerstjerne, 2020).

Methodology

The correctional research design is adapted for this study. The correctional research design is a research design that examines relationships, between variables with less influence on the variable by the research (Sharma, 2010). The population of this study comprises of 9130 undergraduate and post graduate students of three privately-owned universities currently operating in FCT Abuja. The sample size of 383 for this study was determined through the application of Taro Yamane formula (Amadi, 2021). The convenience sampling techniques was employed to reach the respondents in their various campuses while receiving lectures. Primary was collected through the questionnaire, while secondary was obtained through the Internet, Text Books and Journal obtained from Baze University library and the Researcher's library. To test the validity of the Questions in the Questionnaire prepared for this study as the primary data collection instrument, a pilot study was conducted with selected students of Baze University Abuja with copies of the Questionnaire. The reliability of the research instrument for this study was tested using the Chronbach Alpha method and through the application of the SPSS Version

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

26.0. The Questionnaire used for this study was administered and retrieved personally by the Researcher. The data generated for this study were analyzed with Descriptive Statistics method; while the hypotheses postulated were tested with the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Model. These were executed through the application of SPSS Version 20.0.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between Service Delivery Capabilities and Students satisfaction in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T, Abuja. Specifically, the study was guided by the following objectives:

- (1) examine the extent of relationship between service culture and students' satisfaction in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja;
- (2) evaluate the extent of relationship between service responsiveness and students' satisfaction in privately-owned universities in F.C.T. Abuja;
- (3) investigate the extent of relationship between service quality and students' satisfaction in privately-owned universities in F.C.T. Abuja; and
- (4) examine the extent of relationship between employee engagement and students' engagement in privately- owned universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Research Questions

To realize the aim and objectives of this study, the following questions were raised:

- i. To what extent does service culture relate with students' satisfaction in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja?
- ii. To what extent does service responsiveness by privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja relate to students' satisfaction?
- iii. To what extents does service quality relate with students' satisfaction in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja?
- iv. To what extent does employee engagement relate with students' satisfaction in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been postulated in accordance with the objectives and questions of the study.

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between service culture and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between service culture and students referrals in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja.

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between service responsiveness and increased students enrollment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja.

HO₄: There is no significant relationship between service responsiveness and students referrals in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T. Abuja.

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

HO₅: There is no significant relationship between service quality and increased students enrollment in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T. Abuja.

HO₆: There is no significant relationship between service quality and students referrals in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

HO₇: There is no significant relationship between employee engagement and increased students enrollment in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

HO₈: There is no significant relationship between employee engagement and students referrals in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Conceptual Review

There is no need emphasizing the importance of university education. The growing population of Nigeria gave rise to increasing need for more universities. Privately owned universities became relevant given the inability of government owned universities to cope with the increasing need and demand for university education; and also the rise in social vices such as cultism and other forms of criminality prevalent in government owned universities (Madu,2016). The increasing number of privately owned university is the bases of intense competition in the university system especially among the privately-owned universities. Furthermore, the hard economic situation has also been identified by (Teya,2019) to be another reason behind the inability to break even by privately-owned universities in

Nigeria. To overcome these problems, there is need for privately-owned universities to strategically improve on their service delivery capabilities.

Concept of Service Delivery Capabilities

Zeithaml and Bitner (2000) state that 'services include all economic activities whose output is not a physical product or construction, is generally consumed at the time it is produced, provides added value in forms (such as convenience, amusement, timeliness, comfort or health) that are essentially intangible concerns of its first purchaser'. This definition portrays the fact that services are rendered through tangible entities such as teaching aids, but the core product component is not visible. Therefore delivering services is key to customer satisfaction, hence the need to develop efficient and effective service delivery capabilities and strategies.

Service delivery system involves all activities by a service oriented organization (such as a privately owned university) aimed at ensuring the availability and affordability of the services for customer patronage and satisfaction (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2000). Practically, every service delivery system should aim at creating value to both the customers and the organization and should also possess the ability of engaging the service delivery employees (or frontline employees) to enable them deliver value to the customers (Palmer,2005).

Elements of Service Delivery System

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

There are four key elements that make up the service delivery system of every service organization. These elements are: Service

culture, Employee engagement, Service Quality, Employee and customer experience. This is represented in figure 2.1 below.

Service Delivery System

Figure 2.1: Elements of Service Delivery System for Service Organization

Source: Ankerstjerne, P., (2017). Service Management, isspost.

Service Culture

In every service oriented organization such as the university, employees are major determinants of efficient and effective service delivery. But it is important to note that the behavior and in fact the effectiveness and efficiency of the employee depends greatly on the culture of the organization or the pervasive norms and values that determine the behavior of all employees of the organization. Service culture is also referred to as cooperate or organizational culture. Zenith and Bitner (2000) define service culture as “the pattern of shared values and beliefs that give the members of an organization meaning, and provide them with the rules for behavior in the organization”. culture can also be defined informally as “what is obtainable in a particular environment (organization), or how things are done here”. Services culture explains the norms of the service organization. It is a set of overriding principles that give the organization

and its process of delivering services to the customer’s satisfaction. Once this culture is established it influences all other activities of the organization. Service culture can be reflected in the form of:

- Leadership principles (rules and regulation)
- Norms (unfriendly Leadership)
- Work habit and Vision
- Mission and values

Employee Engagement

A well-defined service culture is preceded with employee employment to deliver the service. Employee engagement is the link between the product (service) and the executive of the excellent service model. This means that service can only be delivery through the employees. Variables that need to be considered under this include:

- Employee attitude
- Effectiveness of human resources process
- Availability and accessibility of employees

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

- Employees experience on the services and the service delivery system

It is important to further stress that the ability of the university to realize its objective of customer (student) satisfaction depends on the productivity of the staff (academic and non-academic) of the university. Lussier (2006) states that the employee's ability to work successfully in an organization determines the employee's productivity. This also measures the ability of the employee to adapt and operate in accordance to the service or cooperate culture of the organization. Employee's behavior can be predicted through his/her personality, perception and attitude (Lussier, 2006).

“Personality is a combination of behavioral, mental, and emotional traits that define an individual employee”.

“Perception is a process of selecting, organizing, and interpreting information around ones' (employee) environment”.

“Attitudes are positive or negative evaluation of people, things and situation; they are the major factors in determining the performance of an employee” (Krasner & Ullmann, 1973).

In addition to understanding the personality, perception and attitude of employees, the nature of customer-oriented services demands that employees in a highly service-oriented product like the university must be persons adequately trained in their skills and how to deliver their services. That means skills in their

chosen profession, and skills in delivering academic services to students for adequate satisfaction.

Service Quality

This represents the measure and determinant of customer satisfaction; it includes strategies for managing performance system by the service organization through the engagement of employees. The major determining variables that constitute service quality include: reliability responsiveness, tangibles, assurance and empathy (Berry & Parasuraman, 1991). These variables are briefly explained as follows.

Reliability:

This refers to the ability of the university to deliver the university education services as expected by the students. Not only do students expect to graduate as expected, but also to be able to acquire the needed knowledge as promised by the universities in their mission statements.

Tangibles:

This includes the ability, to showcase or ensure the appearance, availability and functionality of physical facilities, equipment (modern teaching aid such as electronic board, goggle class room, Internet and Data Services, public address system and comfortable classroom), experience lectures with relevant qualifications, equipped library, secured and neat environment.

Assurance:

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

This is the ability of academic and non-academic staff to show courtesy and to convey trust and confidence to students.

Empathy

This is the ability of academic and nonacademic staff to freely and willingly provide caring and individualized attention to students. Listening to students when they call or make couplaniarts, and providing or offering solutions to their academic problems when they have such.

Responsiveness:

This implies the willingness to deliver prompt educational service to the students. This depend on the accuracy of teaching aids and the application of integrated communication technology (ICT) in delivering lectures and other auxiliary services without hitches at the least time. It also includes the ability to provide or respond to student's academic needs and inquiries. It is the willingness and unalloyed ability of the universities relevant staff to respond to complaints and inquiries from students and promptly providing solutions to the inquiries or complaints (Zeithmil & Bitner, 2000). The emphasis of the Responsiveness of Service Delivery Capabilities includes:

- (i) Promptness in responding to students' complaints and or inquiries
- (ii) Reducing the steps and length for delivering and receiving services to students
- (iii) Flexibility and ability to customize services according to students needs

- (iv) Constantly requesting and obtaining feedback from students on their satisfaction of the quality of services they receive from the university
- (v) Continuous improvements on the quality of services to the students based on students' request.

Concept of Students Satisfaction

The first step in every marketing practice is identification of customer need. Every other effort of marketing is aimed at delivering this identified need to the customer satisfaction and or the satisfaction of the marketer whose marketing objective must be realized through the marketing process. The worst dilemma to every marketer is for the customer to experience cognitive dissonance. This is as a result of dissatisfaction experienced by the customer after consumption of the product (kerin et. al., 2003). The difficulty in measuring customer satisfaction gives the impetus to understand the meaning of customer satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction is the customers' evaluation of service in terms of whether that service has meet their needs and expectation; failure to meet needs and expectations is assured to result to dissatisfaction with the service (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000). As identified earlier, organizational success is not only measured in financial (profit-after-tax) terms. Financial terms are inadequate because they fail to recognize the importance of customer satisfaction which is the main driving

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

force of the firms future market share and profit ability (Walker et. al. 2003).

Customer satisfaction is the ability of the privately owned university to meet student expectations. The marketing concept established the fact that customer satisfaction is the basis for realizing the organizations' goals and objectives. That means that until a customer is satisfied, all efforts aimed at efficient and affective service delivery is a waste (Hawkins et. al., 2000). Further more, Copley, 2017 identifies reasons why customer satisfaction is important to include:

- (1) It is an indicator of customer repeat purchase and patronize
- (2) It is a good instrument to avoid or curb consumerism and environmentalism.
- (3) It is a major differentiator among competing organization.
- (4) It improves customers lifeline value (CCV) which in turn attracts increase revenue to the organization; and
- (5) It enables the organization retain existing customers which is cheaper than acquiring new ones.

Measures of Students Satisfaction

Students' satisfaction comprises of factors that can be used to explain the level of satisfaction that students derive from the services of the privately-owned universities. Students' satisfaction can be defined as "a short – term attitude resulting from an evaluation of student's educational experience, service and facilities". It shows the ability and willingness

of students to respond positively or negatively to the services delivered to them by their institutions based on the satisfaction derived (Manzoor, 2013). It also reflects the perceived reliability and the general opinion of the students with regards to the quality of the services rendered by the universities as a result of the students' experience with the services delivered to them by the privately-owned university. It is the positive feeling of happiness that the students show over the services of the university, or the show of happiness to be identified as a student of the university. For the purpose of this study, Students satisfaction in privately-owned universities can be better evaluated through increase in students' enrollment and student's referrals to privately-owned universities (Stephens, 2014). These are briefly explained as follows.

Increased student's enrolment is the willingness of students to maintain their studentship and to enroll for further studies in the privately-owned universities given the level of satisfaction derived from the services of the university. It amounts to the level of loyalty the students are willing to exhibit in favour of the privately-owned university given the services delivered to the students by the university. Increased student's enrolment guarantees increased funds to the university through receipts of school fees promptly paid.

Referral is an act of referring some prospective student's; parents and other individuals seeking admission to the privately-owned

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

university. Student's referrals consist of the testimonies by the students about the quality of services delivered by the university, thereby recommending and encouraging their peers, siblings and other relations and the general public to patronize the University Admission and studies. The use of referrals through student's can be achieved through offering of gifts to students (such as meal ticket, sport skits, sports tickets and gift cards) to students as an encouragement or compensation for attracting prospective students to the university. Also, the Alumni association of the university can also be utilized as good referral to attract increased student's enrollment.

To further realize the needed level of satisfaction for students in privately-owned universities, there is need for high level and constant interaction between the university and the students. This can be enhanced by factors including: technologically-enhanced teaching aids with reliable Internet Services, conducive learning environment and Promotional activities by the universities.

The emergence and growing positive impact of technology has created provisions for modern teaching aids. Also, the prevalence of social vices among students, and pandemics ravaging the world create the need for the use of modern teaching aids in delivering university education services to students. The anticipated aim of these modern teaching aids is to enhance interaction between staff and students, and also to enhance assimilation of knowledge by students. Some of these modern teaching aids include: Computers and laptops, Android iphones, Internet services, electronic board, Video teaching (goggle classroom), Online library, Online dictionary/encyclopedia, and Online exam/quiz and plagiarism test (turnitin).

Conducive Learning Environment

Effective and efficient delivery of university education services, and adequate learning is consummated in a conducive environment. Conducive environment for acquiring university education include factors and other facilities that guarantees and encourages effective and efficient transmission of knowledge and skill from the university staff to students. Some of these factors include: Comfortable hostels and accommodation for students and staff, Constant presence of armed security personnel in the campus, Comfortable classroom equipped with modern teaching aids, Equipped libraries, neat surroundings, Recreation facilities, and Restaurants and relaxation facilities/spots.

Promotional Activities

Promotional activities include all conscious efforts made by privately-owned universities aimed at communicating value of their services to the target market. The underlying philosophy for communicating university education services is that the university may have the best teaching aids and the most conducive environment, but if all these are not communicated in such manner that portrays better value to the target market, students may not be attracted to the university. Traditionally, promotional tools include: Advertising, Personal Selling, Sales Promotion, Public Relations and Publicity, Internet and Interactive Marketing, Direct Marketing and Packaging. But specifically, privately-owned universities can utilize the following modes for promoting their services: Utilize staff and students as promotional tools, showcase your services, utilize online channels perfectly, Host and publicize special events by the university, invest heavily on the university website,

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Utilize the Alumli for testimonies, and organize easy-to-enter contest for target markets.

Operational Conceptual Framework

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Figure 2.2 showing Conceptual Framework for the study on Service Delivery capabilities and students satisfaction in privately-owned Universities.

Sources: Zeithaml & Bitner (2000); and Berry & Parasuraman (1991).

From Figure 2.2 above, service delivery capabilities by privately-owned universities in Nigeria are the independent (Predictor) variables that determine the level of satisfaction the students will derive from the services of the privately-owned universities. The service delivery capabilities are made up of factors (Predictor variables) including Service culture, Employee engagement, Service quality and customer experience. To execute these services delivery capabilities, major factors (moderating variables) within the university environment include: Experienced (Academic and Non-academic) staff, Modern teaching aids, conducive learning environment and promotion activities. These shall be used to realize student's satisfaction (dependents or criterion variables). Student's satisfaction can come in the form of increased student's enrollment, higher ratings by the relevant agencies and the general public and testimonies by students.

Theoretical Review and Framework

The Theory of Expectation

The theory of expectation is a very popular theory used in describing the nature of satisfaction derived from a product by a consumer. Wikipedia, 2021 states that the structure of the theory was developed by

Richard L. Oliver in 1977 and 1980 after two series of studies. This theory seeks to give explanations to post-purchase and post-adoption satisfaction as a function of expectation, perceived performance and disconfirmation of beliefs. The popularity of the theory is linked to the extent that most scholars modify the name and explanations. Some of these names are disconfirmation theory and expectation disconfirmation theory. In further elaboration, Baska, 1992 states that the philosophy of the Expectation theory believes that a consumer satisfaction or dissatisfaction is a result of the consumer comparison of performance of a product with already set standards of performance, and that the possible outcomes can emanate from that belief. These outcomes include 1. positive disconfirmation which results when performance is perceived by consumer to be better than the anticipated expectations, thus causing the consumer to be delighted; 2. zero disconfirmation which result when performance is perceived to be exactly equal to expectation, thus causing the consumer to be likely satisfied; and 3. negative disconfirmation which results when the performance is lower than the consumer's expectation, thus causing the consumer to be dissatisfied.

This theory is related to our study because the philosophy of the theory is based on consumer satisfaction based on past experience. Unfortunately, the theory is not directly linked to educational services. Figure 2.0 below

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

provides a diagrammatic representation of theory.

Figure 2.3 showing model of expectation confirmation theory.

Source: Wikipedia, 2021.

The Theory of Assimilation (Dissonance)

This theory was developed Festinger (1957) but popularly referred as the theory of Dissonance. The Theory states that every consumer makes a kind of cognitive comparison between expectations concerning the product, and the same products' anticipated performance. By so doing, when there is any disagreement between expectations and the products anticipated performance, dissonance will occur. Anderson (1973) as quoted in Isaac and Rusu (2014) that state that the customer's feelings or levels of satisfaction is determined by post-usage evaluation, and that most times, consumers try to eliminate dissonance by adjusting their perceptions of a products so as to bring the product performance closer to consumers' expectation. The implication of this theory in that some customers try to justify the level of satisfaction derivable. This implies that satisfaction derivable from a product in based on the combination of several products

attributes. Some good product attributes may erase the weakness of some attribute to neutralize dissonance from such product.

Theory of Contrast

This theory was propounded by Houland, Harvey and Sheerif (1957). The philosophy behind the theory provided a credible alternative to the theory of Evaluation and post –usage process as presented by the Assimilation (Dissonance theory). According to Dawes et al (1972) as quoted in Isaac and Rusu (2014), Contrast Theory is seen as the as the ability to magnify the differences between one's own attitude and the attitude and the attitude represented by the opinion of others. In their contribution, Isaac and Rusa (2014) elaborate the Contrast Theory to mean that whenever customers experience disconfirmation, they try to minimize the discrepancy between their previous and actual products performance by shifting their evaluations away from their expectations. This Theory in similar to the

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

Assimilation Theory but the difference between the two is that while The Assimilation Theory beliefs that consumers will try to minimize the expectation performance discrepancy, the Contrast Theory recommends a surprise act that can lead to magnifying the discrepancy. For instance, if a promise of a product performance is exaggerated during promotion and the customer's experiences something less than the promise, the product may be rejected out rightly, while under-promising and higher experience would mean increased patronage more.

This theory is related to our study because it places high emphases on product quality without compromise. Privately-owned universities are in business to make profit; furthermore they do not get financial support from the government. So any short fall in service quality may reduce student's enrolment and negatively affect profit. Unfortunately the study is not directed at students or privately owned university, yet it is relevant to our study.

Theory of Human Service Delivery

According to Reader: 2017, the Theory of Human Service Delivery explains an understanding of how people work within systems to deliver service. The theory sees people (personnel) as the major resources or tool for delivering service. Since services are judged partly by subjective criteria, it is difficult to understand the quality of services. The underlying philosophy around this theory is explained under the following headings:

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Intangibility

Services cannot be touched or handled, hence they are intangible. They only exist as events; they cannot be resold or shared between customers and the parties involved. Therefore delivering a service to a person requires using qualified personnel to interact with the customer with a view of satisfying customer needs. Also, effective and efficient delivery of service requires that the system designer must consider the human element involved to ensure that the people delivering the service are capable of interacting positively and effectively with the market to realize the needed outcome.

Variability

Given the variability nature of service, the service organization must ensure consistency in quality improvement of their services. Furthermore, a serious and constant effort must be made to obtain feedback from customer and to understand how best to improve services. This also necessitates constant training of personnel.

Limit

This explains the limit of service that personnel of a service organization can carry. The theory beliefs that personnel should not be stretched further than what he/she can accomplish in a given time. Therefore to increase the quantity and quality of any service, it is necessary to increase the personnel involved. This is because the more difficult the service is, the more costly it will be to satisfy customer.

Ideology

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

The theory stresses the importance of clearly defined organizational ideology. To motivate the service personnel, the organization's mission and vision that portray its ideology must be clearly communicated to the personnel. This will enable the personnel aspire to realizing the organizations' goals with little or no supervision.

For the purpose of this study, the Theory of Human Service Delivery is adopted as the theoretical framework.

Empirical Review

For the purpose of this study the following studies were reviewed:

“Service delivery in Higher education (HE): A comparative study between public and private universities” was executed by Hogue, Razak and Zohora, (2013) with the principal aim to find out the effectiveness of Service delivery between public and private Higher education institutions as perceived by the students. The study investigated the differences in four areas and the relationship between the management and the administration indicators and the other three indicators in the admission, facilities and teaching. Descriptive and linear regression analyses were used to analyze the data. Total of 400 students from different universities including the public and privately owned. The findings reveal that private Higher education institutions have fared significantly better in all area except in the academic teaching aspect in comparison to their Public counterparts. With regards to admission, the private Higher

education institutions fared better were student highly rate the website effectiveness and the use of social media as offered by these private higher education institutions, as to be highly informative to them. The public education institutions view facilities as a mere addition, whereas the private education institutions see them as an initial sizeable investment outlay. In the teaching sector of excellence, the finding skewed more positively towards public education institutions. The study recommends public Universities to be lenient in the area of admission procedures and infrastructural facilities while private Universities to be attentive to ensure quality teaching. This study favorably relates to most of our research objectives especially the service culture, employee engagement and service quality. The envisaged gap in the reviewed study is that it focuses more on comparison between public University and Private Universities, but the recommendation is similar to the objectives of our study.

“Students perception of service delivery in the University” was carried out by Teya, Edwin M of the centre for extra moral studies, University of Nairobi, Kenya in 2019. The objective of this study is to determine the influence of service delivery by Universities on Students perception given the increasing competitive environment the universities are currently facing. Other main aims are to establish the relationship between dimensions of service quality and students' satisfaction, and to access students'

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

expectations in terms of higher educational services quality that was originally developed by Parasuraman et.al., (1988). Three assumptions were formulated about the relationship between service delivery dimensions and perceived service delivery. Data was collected from 44 respondents using questionnaire and SERQUAL Instruments from students of Nairobi Kisii extral moral centre. Major findings by the study include: (i) students are dissatisfied with the state of equipment (that is inadequate up to date equipments); (ii) students expected that high service delivery should have been maintained to the time; (iii) students are conceived with their perception of the quality of service provided; and (iv) students are not satisfied with the quality of the administration by the university and the centre in particular. The recommendation include: (i) there is need for the centre (and school) administrators to take decisive role in removing barriers to students satisfaction by listening and responding to students expectations, by continuously measuring students perceptions, implementing a customer focused mission statement, rewarding service-oriented support staff and revising practices and procedures that interfere with satisfying students; and (ii) there is need also to respond to students feedback: the simple act of surveying students opinions regarding their level of satisfaction with college services and programs will show that the University cares. The study concluded that its funding will assist University marketers and

practitioners to develop and implement services, marketing strategic for achieving a high quality service, and enhancing students' satisfaction. The study is relevant to our research objectives as it identifies factors that attract students satisfaction. Though the study was not specific on privately-owned Universities "Students' Perception of Teacher's Classroom Effectiveness on their Self-concept in Lagos metropolis" was executed in 2014 in Lagos by Ibrahim, A.W. The aim of this study is to determine the difference between the student's perception of their teacher's classroom behavior and their self-concept, and to examine gender difference in student's perception of their teachers behavior. The study also investigated the difference between the students' perception of their academic performance in school and their self-concept. All these are aimed at improving the quality of teacher-student interaction in the classroom. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The study population consists of adolescent students in government owned secondary schools in Lagos state. Questionnaire was administered to sample size of 240 randomly selected from the classrooms. Data was analyzed using one-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and fishers' protected t-test statistical techniques. The major funding include: there is significant difference between student's perception of teacher's classroom effectiveness and their self-concepts; there is significant gender difference in students' perception of their teachers' behavior;

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

and there is a significant difference between students perception of their academic performance and their self-concept. The study concludes that the kinds of roles the teacher assume have profound effect on the perception of students toward them and their self-concept. The study is relevant to our study because its objective is aimed at identifying factors that contribute to student's satisfaction.

“ICT Competence and lecturers job efficiency: A study of two universities in South-South Nigeria” was carried out by Akpan C.P., in 2014. The main aim of the study is to identify the influence of ICT competence on lecturer's job efficiency in Nigeria University. Sample size of 500 university teachers were randomly selected from a population of 1795. Descriptive Analysis and Regression Model were employed to text the data and hypotheses postulated. The result of the study reveals that male & female lecturers did not differ significantly in their level of ICT competence; lecturers with high ICT competence were found to be more effective in classroom instruction, research/publication, and communication and record keeping than those with moderate and low ICT competence; and the level of ICT competence of lecturers significantly enhanced their job efficiency. Based on these findings, the study recommends that: lecturers should be motivated to develop their ICT competence as this has been found to improve job efficacy for high productivity; university management should encourage lecturers to participate in ICT training

programs; and ICT facilities should be provided in lecturers offices to enhance their job efficacy. This study is relevant to our study as it conforms to the relevance of one of our independent variables (that is employee engagement) which describes the relevance and competence of service personnel as part of service delivery capabilities to attract students' satisfaction.

“Improving Access to University Education: The Case of National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN)” was carried out by Nnaka, C.V in 2014. This paper examines open and distance learning in the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), and the role it plays in improving accessibility to university education for personal, community and national development. The study also analyzed the challenges facing NOUN and further proffers solutions capable of ameliorating the problems. The study is a descriptive essay with the National Open University of Nigeria as a case study. The study established that the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) is faced with several challenges in its bid to provide quality, cost effective and flexible education to Nigerians through open and distance learning. Some of these challenges include: low internet connectivity in Nigeria; most of the facilitating lecturers lack basic skills to operate in an open and distance learning system; some of the lecturers lack the skill of delivering their lectures in electronic format because they are not ICT compliant and this is seriously affecting

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

the delivery of education services; consistent delay in production and delivery of instructional materials; most of the students are not computer literate, hence they have difficulty accessing the lectures electronically; and weak or unsteady supply of electricity. The study recommends that the Federal Government should adequately provide funding to universities so as to realize the essence of education; secondly, the federal government should ensure the provision of adequate electricity to every part of the country. The study is relevant to our study with particular reference to service quality which is one of the independent variables aimed at ensuring adequate service delivery of university services for student's satisfaction.

“Appraisal of the availability and utilization of information and communication technology in the higher education system in Nigeria” was executed in Abuja in 2014 by Obuozobe, J-G & Aneke Emeka Paul. The study examines the availability and utilization of information and communication technology in the Nigeria Higher Education system and its implication for National Development. Data for the study were obtained mainly from secondary sources on ICT and national development through higher education. The major findings of the study include: inadequate funding, insufficient skill and human resources, power supply and inadequate infrastructure were the major constraints to application and utilization of ICT in Nigeria higher education system. Based on

these, the study recommends amongst others that a substantial part of the tertiary education trust fund (TETF) be directed towards ICT facility provision so as to improve institutional capacity building the ICT driven. This study is relevant to our study as it describes the major environmental factors that affect quality service delivery by higher institutions to attract student's satisfaction.

“Managing Academic Service Delivery in South—South Nigeria Universities for National Education Transformation” was carried out by Akabue B. A. in 2016. The study is aimed at identifying appropriate management approach for managing service delivery in universities in South—South region of Nigeria. Three hypotheses were postulated based on a survey-design approach. Stratified random sampling technique was applied to select a sample size of 200 respondents from a population of 322 made up of Deans and Heads of Departments in four Federal Universities. Data were collected with the use of Academic Service Delivery Management Questionnaire (ASDMQ). Data collected were analyzed using population t-test of single mean and independent t-test statistical techniques. The following findings emerged: managing academic service delivery at the departmental level is significantly low; managing academic service delivery at the faculty level is significantly low; and there is no significant difference in managing academic service delivery between departments and faculties in South—South universities. Based on

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

these findings, the study recommends that Deans of facilities and Heads of Departments should give priority attention to academic service delivery to enhance student's academics outcomes, quality education and national education transformation. This study is relevant to our study as it dwells on service culture which is one of our independent variables. It also emphasizes on service quality which is also one of the pillars of our study.

“The Quality of Educational Service and its effect on Student's Satisfaction: An Empirical Study on Students of Alrifaaq Private University in Libya” was executed in Libya in 2017 by Ali Abdul Salam Kammur. The main aim of the study is to demonstrate the effect of educational services on student's satisfaction in Private Universities in Libya. To realize the objectives, the study administered questionnaire on statistically selected students of Alrifaaq Private University in Libya. Data obtained and hypotheses postulated were tested through Analytical Descriptive Approach. The major findings from the study include: the level of evaluation of education service quality in private university is high; there is an impact of educational service quality and supervision quality on student's satisfaction; and there is also an impact of educational service quality on supervision quality. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the university should keep emphasizing on commitment and continuous development of the educational plan and improve the adopted programs by the

university to increase the quality of its education process. This study is relevant to our study because its emphasis is on service quality and employee engagement as parameters for realizing student's satisfaction. Though the study was executed in Libya, but the result can as well be applied in Nigeria.

“Professional development practice and Service Delivery of Academic Staff at Kampala International University and Kyambogo University” was carried out in Kampala Uganda in 2019 by Kulthum Nabuniya, Hilary Tusiime Mukwanda & Robert Kyaligonza. The study is principally aimed at examining the relationship between professional development practices and teaching, research and community service at Kampala International University (KIU) and Kyambogo University (KYU). The responsees from 466 respondents through a questionnaire were utilized for the study. Data obtained was analyzed with the simple linear regression. The major findings include: professional development practices are significantly related with teaching service. The study therefore recommends among others that University Administrators should promote mentoring, coaching, offer of study and training of their academic staff. Though this study was executed in Kampala Uganda, it is relevant to our study as it emphasis on academic staff development to enhance quality service delivery for satisfaction of University Students. This is one of the implications of employee engagement and

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

quality services as implied in our independent variables.

“Assessing University Students Satisfaction with Service Delivery: Implications for Education Management” was executed by Uduak Imo Ekpoh in Akwa Ibom and Cross-Rivers States and published in 2018. The aim of this study is to investigate student’s satisfaction with service delivery tools (including library, health, transportation, information and communication technology (ICT), and hostel service). Also investigated is the extent to which student’s satisfaction with service delivery varied with types of institutions. Survey research design was adapted for the study with questionnaire used to elicit primary data. A sample size of 1466 was drawn from a population of undergraduates in four universities in Akwa-Ibom and Cross-Rivers States. The data obtain were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while the hypotheses postulated with the study variables were tested using the t-test. The major findings include: majority of respondents indicated dissatisfaction with library, hostel as well as information and communication services; the respondents showed moderate satisfaction with health and transportation services; student’s satisfaction with service delivery in terms of library and health services significantly deferred by their institution’s affiliations; there is no significant difference in student’s satisfaction with transportation, ICT and hostel services. Based on the findings, the study recommends that there should be an acceptance and

satisfactory improvement in service delivery in universities especially all services that contribute to student’s academic life in the university. This study is relevant to our study as practically demonstrates how to realize students’ satisfaction through service delivery instruments. This is in consonance with our dependent variable.

“Quality Service Delivery and Satisfaction in Public Universities in South – Eastern Nigeria” was carried out by Ovat Okpa in 2019 using South- Eastern States. The aim of the study is to establish the relationship between quality service delivery and students’ satisfaction in public universities in South – Eastern of Nigeria. The descriptive Survey research design was adopted with a population of 1231 final year students of universities in the study area. Questionnaire was administered to a sample size of 200 final year students. Data obtain were tested using descriptive statistics and person product correction coefficient. The major findings show that: there is a significant positive relationship between quality teaching, curriculum, academic advising and physical facilities and students’ satisfaction. The study therefore recommends among others that university management should be more proactive towards infrastructural development and in providing adequate facilities for students to enhance their work as well as create good learning environment. This Study relates to our service quality and students’ satisfaction variables, hence its relevance to our study.

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

“Indicators of Student’s Satisfaction of Quality Education Services in some selected Universities in Ghana” was carried out in Ghana by Amaoka & Kasamoah – Gyimah and published in 2020. The objective of the study is to examine the factors that contribute to student’s satisfaction of education services as a quality assurance module for universities. The study utilizes a descriptive cross – sectional survey design. Adapting a multi – stage sampling procedure, the opinion of 1500 students from three public universities in Ghana was obtained through a questionnaire and utilized. The questionnaire was developed to measure students’ satisfaction (SS) and quality assurance (QA) (to measure satisfaction of students related to educational services that they receive in their campus). Analysis of movement structures (AMOS) was used to both validate the instrument and test the hypotheses. Findings of the study include that: instructional environment, technological environment and psychological environment are predictors of student’s satisfaction in the contest of how students see academic institution to be quality centered. The study therefore recommends that universities should emphasize and prioritize student’s satisfaction in their quality assurance framework as a way of sustaining quality provisions of educational services; universities

should invest in technological infrastructure, monitor instructional dynamics and bring student’s closer to academic staff through students consultative meeting so as to realize student’s satisfaction; and universities internal quality assurance department should assess quality educational services from the causes of academic experience that make student’s satisfied. This study is related to our study because it emphasizes on realizing students’ satisfaction in universities in Ghana who has a similar academic culture with Nigeria.

Gap in Literature

The gap in literature identified in this study after the review is that there is less emphasis on the utilization of students’ experience in decision making by privately-owned universities. Student’s satisfaction should act as the pivotal point or source of information to shape decisions regarding service (organizational) culture, the nature of employee to be engaged, the service quality to be provided and the anticipated rate of responsiveness to student’s needs. Therefore, further studies can be executed with regard to how to obtain and utilize students experience for decisions on how best to satisfy the students for the purpose of realizing the objectives of privately-owned universities in Nigeria and developing countries

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Data Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

Table 4.1: Questionnaire Distribution to Respondents and Retrieval

State	Issued Questionnaire	Retrieved Questionnaire	Used Questionnaire	Percentage (%) Used Questionnaire
FCT	383	380	380	99.2

Source: Survey Data, 2021.

Table 4.1 shows that out of 383 questionnaires distributed, 380 representing 99.2% were properly filled and returned. Further analysis and discussion are based on this figure.

4.2.1 Demographic Analysis

This section presents the demography of the respondents and the selected demography considered in the process of this research include; gender, age bracket category of respondents and years in school.

Gender of Respondents

Table 4.2: Distribution of Respondents according to Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	210	55.3	55.3	55.3
Male	170	44.7	44.7	100.0
Total	380	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2021).

Figure 4.1: pie chart distribution of gender responses.

Table 4.2 shows that 210 frequency representing 55.3% of the respondents were female while 170 representing 44.7% of the respondents were male. This was further simplified with figure 4.1 which presents the responses with pie chart. This suggests that the privately-owned universities in FCT Abuja are dominated by female.

Age Bracket of Respondents

Table 4.3: Distribution of Respondents Base of Age Bracket

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid <18	15	3.9	3.9	3.9
18-22	205	53.9	53.9	57.9
23-26	125	32.9	32.9	90.8
27&Above	35	9.2	9.2	100.0
Total	380	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2021).

Figure 4.2: Bar chart showing Age Bracket of respondents.

From table 4.3, out of the valid 380 copies of questionnaire returned, respondents who are under 18 years were 15 persons representing 3.9%, respondents within the age bracket of 18-22 answered 205 copies representing 53.9%, age 23-26 answered 127 copies representing 32.9%, while age 27 and above answered 35 copies representing 9.2% of the total respondents. The bar chart in figure 4.2

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

shows the distribution of respondents along age bracket. This finding indicates that age 18-22 constitutes the higher proportion of the respondents.

Program Category of Respondents

Table 4.4: Distribution of Respondents Based of Program Category

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Post Graduate	25	6.6	6.6	6.6
	Undergraduate	355	93.4	93.4	100.0
	Total	380	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2021).

Figure 4.3: Pie chart showing Category of respondents.

Table 4.4 shows that 25 frequency representing 6.6% of the respondents are post graduate students of the universities while 355 frequency representing 93.4% of the total respondents were undergraduate students. This was also represented with pie chart in figure 4.3 which suggest that majority of the respondents were undergraduates.

Years spend in School

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Two Years	30	7.9	7.9	7.9
	Three Years	205	53.9	53.9	61.8
	Four Years	110	28.9	28.9	90.8
	Five Years Above	35	9.2	9.2	100.0
	Total	380	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2021).

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Figure 4.4: Bar chart showing years spend in university.

Table 4.4, shows that out of the valid 380 copies of questionnaire returned, respondents who had spent two years in the universities answered 30 copies representing 7.9% of respondents, three years answered 205 copies representing 53.9%, four years answered 110 copies representing 28.9% while five years and above answered 35 frequencies representing 9.2% of the total questionnaire. This implies that the majority of respondents are in the third years of their studies followed by fourth year, while year two and five years above were low. The bar chart in figure 4.4 also simplified this distribution.

Univariate Analysis

This section is primarily concern with the analysis of the univariate variables relating to

the respondents' views on the questions contained in the various sections and items on the research instruments. The primary analysis entailed the assessment of the distribution and application of statistical analysis on each variable as a means of examining the tendencies of these variables. The study variables included two major variables; the predictor variable and the criterion variable. The predictor variable is Service Delivery, which has service culture, service responsiveness, service quality and employee engagement as dimensions and the criterion variable of student satisfaction which adopted increased students enrolment and student referral as measures.

The research instrument generated data that showed the degree of agreement of the major variable, as well as the dimensions and measures. The data obtained from the field was measured using a 5-point Likert scale based on (VHE) Very High Extent (5), (HE) High Extent (4), (ME) Moderate Extent (3), (LE) Low Extent (2) and (VLE) Very Low Extent (1). As such interpretations for each variable is premised on the extent to which it's mean distributions reflect either significant evidence (where $x > 3.00$) or the extent to which it reflects insignificant evidence (where $x < 3.00$).

Mean Analysis of Data

Table 4.5: Distribution for indicator of Service Culture and Increased students' Enrolment in Private-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Descriptive Statistics

Indicators	N	Min	Max	Sum	Mean	Std.	
						Deviation	Variance
SERVICE CULTURE AND INCREASE STUDENTS' ENROLLMENT	380	1.00	5.00	1222.80	3.2179	1.31462	1.728
You are satisfied with the university's service culture.	380	1	5	868	2.28	1.400	1.961
You are satisfied with rules and regulations in the university and willing to enroll for further studies.	380	1	5	1424	3.75	1.351	1.825
You are satisfied with the leadership of the university and willing to enroll for further studies.	380	1	5	1363	3.59	1.392	1.937

Table; 4.5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 & 11 provide descriptive analyses of the positions of respondents concerning the questions asked on service delivery and students satisfaction. This analysis addresses question 1-4 which examined the effect of service culture, service responsiveness, service quality and employee engagement on increased students enrollment and students referral. The variable is assessed using sets of five (5) and six (6) indicators which assess the respondents' positions on the relationship between the variables.

Research Question 1

To what extent does service culture relate with students satisfaction in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja?

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

You are satisfied with the procedure for obtaining the university service and willing to enroll for further studies.

380	1	5	1108	2.92	1.452	2.109
-----	---	---	------	------	-------	-------

You are satisfied with Promotion activities by the university and willing to enroll for further studies. .

380	1	5	1351	3.56	1.397	1.952
-----	---	---	------	------	-------	-------

Valid N (listwise) 380

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires' data 2021)

The data in (table 4.5) illustrate the summary of the statistics for the dimension of the predictor variable "Service Culture" with summarized values for central tendency as it relates increased students' enrolment based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that three (3) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00, while two (2) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores below the criterion mean of 3.00, based on 5-point likert scale which implied that the response is moderate. In summary, with a grand mean of 3.21, the respondents agreed that the influence of service culture on increased students' enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.

Table 4.6: Distribution for indicator of Service Culture and Students' Referral in Private-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Descriptive Statistics

Indicators	N	Min	Max	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
SERVICE CULTURE AND STUDENTS' REFERRAL	380	1.00	5.00	1200.40	3.1589	1.30532	1.704
You are satisfied with the universitys' service culture.	380	1	5	868	2.28	1.393	1.940
You are satisfied with rules and regulations in the university and willing to recommend the university to others.	380	1	5	1423	3.74	1.340	1.795
You are satisfied with the leadership of the university university and willing to recommend the university to others.	380	1	5	1258	3.31	1.372	1.882

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

You are satisfied with the procedure for obtaining the university service and willing to recommend the university to others.	380	1	5	1104	2.91	1.441	2.075
--	-----	---	---	------	------	-------	-------

You are satisfied with Promotion activities by the university and willing to recommend the university to others.	380	1	5	1349	3.55	1.378	1.900
--	-----	---	---	------	------	-------	-------

Valid N (listwise)	380
--------------------	-----

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires' data 2021)

The data in (table 4.6) also illustrate the summary of the statistics for the dimension of the predictor variable "Service Culture" with summarized values for central tendency as it relates students' referral based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that three (3) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00, while two (2) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores below the criterion mean of 3.00, based on 5-point likert scale which implied that the response is moderate. In summary, with a grand mean of 3.31, the respondents agreed that the influence of service culture on students' referral in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.

Research Question 2

To what extent does service responsiveness by privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja relate to students' satisfaction?

Table 4.7: Distribution for indicator of Service Responsiveness and Increased Students' Enrolment in Private-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Descriptive Statistics

Indicators	N	Min	Max	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
SERVICE RESPONSIVENESS AND INCREASE STUDENTS' ENROLLMENT	380	1.00	5.00	1046.40	2.7537	1.43274	2.053

You are satisfied with the services responsiveness of the university.	380	1	5	966	2.54	1.446	2.091
---	-----	---	---	-----	------	-------	-------

You are willing to enroll for further studies in the university because of the attention given to students compliant.	380	1	5	1075	2.83	1.456	2.121
---	-----	---	---	------	------	-------	-------

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

You are willing to enroll for further studies in the university because of the promptness in responding to students' complaints and request. 380 1 5 985 2.59 1.423 2.026

You are willing to enroll for further studies in the university because of constant contact with the students to ascertain students' satisfaction for possible amendments. 380 1 5 985 2.59 1.473 2.168

You are willing to enroll for further studies in the university because of its flexibility and willingness to customize its services according to student's needs. 380 1 5 1221 3.21 1.575 2.480

Valid N (listwise) 380

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires' data 2021)

The data in (table 4.7) illustrate the summary of the statistics for the dimension of the predictor variable "Service Responsiveness" with summarized values for central tendency as it relates students' enrolment based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that four (4) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores below the criterion mean of 3.00, while only one (1) indicator in the scale had weighted mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00, based on 5-point likert scale which implied that the response is low. With a grand mean of 2.75, the respondents agreed that the influence of service responsiveness on increased students' enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a low extent.

Table 4.8: Distribution for indicator of Service Responsiveness and Students' Referral in Private-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Descriptive Statistics

Indicators	N	Min	Max	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
SERVICE RESPONSIVENESS	380	1.00	5.00	1062.60	2.7963	1.41976	2.016
STUDENTS' REFERRAL							
You are satisfied with the services responsiveness of the university.	380	1	5	957	2.52	1.443	2.081
You are willing to recommend the university to others because of the attention given to students compliant.	380	1	5	1087	2.86	1.453	2.110

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

You are willing to recommend the380 1 5 995 2.62 1.412 1.994
 university to others because of the
 promptness in responding to students'
 complaints and request.

You are willing to recommend the380 1 5 1020 2.68 1.491 2.222
 university to others because of constant
 contact with the students to ascertain
 students' satisfaction for possible
 amendments.

You are willing to recommend the380 1 5 1254 3.30 1.520 2.311
 university to others because of its
 flexibility and willingness to customize
 its services according to student's needs.

Valid N (listwise) 380

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires' data 2021)

The data in (table 4.8) illustrate the summary of the statistics for the dimension of the predictor variable "Service Responsiveness" with summarized values for central tendency as it relates students' referral based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that four (4) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores below the criterion mean of 3.00, while only one (1) indicator in the scale had weighted mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00, based on 5-point likert scale which implied that the response is low. With a grand mean of 2.79, the respondents agreed that the influence of service responsiveness on students' referral in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a low extent.

Research Question 3

To what extents does service quality relate with students satisfaction in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja?

Table 4.9: Distribution for indicator of Service Quality and Increased Students' Enrolment in Private-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Descriptive Statistics

Indicators	N	Mini	Max	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
SERVICE QUALITY AND INCREASE STUDENTS' ENROLLMENT	380	1.00	5.00	1144.60	3.0121	1.48177	2.196
You are satisfied with service quality by the university	380	1	5	1216	3.20	1.565	2.451

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

You are willing to enroll for further studies in380 the university because their services are reliable.	1	5	1204	3.17	1.581	2.499
---	---	---	------	------	-------	-------

You are willing to enroll for further studies in380 the university because of the teaching aids and good learning environment.	1	5	1047	2.76	1.416	2.006
--	---	---	------	------	-------	-------

You are willing to enroll for further studies in380 the university because Staff empathize with the students.	1	5	1213	3.19	1.572	2.472
---	---	---	------	------	-------	-------

You are willing to enroll for further studies in380 the university because staff give assurance to students.	1	5	1043	2.74	1.487	2.212
--	---	---	------	------	-------	-------

Valid N (listwise) 380

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires' data 2021)

The data in (table 4.9) illustrate the summary of the statistics for the dimension of the predictor variable "Service Quality" with summarized values for central tendency as it relates students' enrolment based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that three (3) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00, while two (2) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores below the criterion mean of 3.00, based on 5-point likert scale which implied that the response is moderate. With a grand mean of 3.01, the respondents agreed that the influence of service quality on increased students' enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.

Table 4.10: Distribution for indicator of Service Quality and Increased Students' Referral in Private-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Descriptive Statistics

Indicator	N	Min	Max	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
SERVICE QUALITY	380	1.00	5.00	1147.60	3.0200	1.47636	2.180
STUDENTS' REFERRAL							
You are satisfied with service quality by the university	380	1	5	1208	3.18	1.566	2.453

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

You are willing to recommend the university to others because their services are reliable.	380	1	5	1214	3.19	1.569	2.463
You are willing to recommend the university to others because of their teaching aids and good learning environment.	380	1	5	1050	2.76	1.411	1.991
You are willing to recommend the university to others because Staff empathize with the students.	380	1	5	1215	3.20	1.562	2.439
You are willing to recommend the university to others because staff give assurance to students.	380	1	5	1051	2.77	1.480	2.190
Valid N (listwise)	380						

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires' data 2021)

The data in (table 4.10) also illustrate the summary of the statistics for the dimension of the predictor variable "Service Quality" with summarized values for central tendency as it relates students' referral based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that three (3) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00, while two (2) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores below the criterion mean of 3.00, based on 5-point likert scale which implied that the response is moderate. With a grand mean of 3.02, the respondents agreed that the influence of service quality on students' referral in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.

Research Question 4

To what extent does employee engagement relate with students satisfaction in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja?

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Table 4.11: Distribution for indicator of Employee Engagement and Increased Students’ Enrolment in Private-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Descriptive Statistics

Indicators	N	Min	Max	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
EMPLOYEE'S ENGAGEMENT AND INCREASE STUDENTS' ENROLLMENT	380	1.00	5.00	1232.60	3.2437	1.44357	2.084
You are satisfied with the attitude and manner of delivering services by the staff of the university.	380	1	5	1311	3.45	1.440	2.074
You are willing to enroll for further studies in the university because the Staff are friendly and have cordial relationship with the students.	380	1	5	1300	3.42	1.437	2.065
You are willing to enroll for further studies in the university because the Staff deliver their lectures to the understanding of students.	380	1	5	1130	2.97	1.480	2.189
You are willing to enroll for further studies in the university because lecturers are accessible and available to students for academic purposes.	380	1	5	1229	3.23	1.464	2.143
You are willing to enroll for further studies in the university because Lecturers produce quiz and exam results promptly and accessible to students.	380	1	5	1193	3.14	1.585	2.511
Valid N (listwise)	380						

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires’ data 2021)

The data in (table 4.11) illustrate the summary of the statistics for the dimension of the predictor variable “Employee Engagement” with summarized values for central tendency as it relates students’ enrolment based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that four (4) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00, while only one (1) indicator in

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

the scale had weighted mean scores below the criterion mean of 3.00, based on 5-point likert scale which implied that the response is moderate. With a grand mean of 3.24, the respondents agreed that the influence of employee engagement on increased students' enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.

Table 4.12: Distribution for indicator of Employee Engagement and Students' Referral in Private-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Descriptive Statistics

Indicators	N	Min	Max	Sum	Mean	Std.	
						Deviation	Variance
EMPLOYEE'S ENGAGEMENT AND STUDENTS' REFERRAL	380	1.00	5.00	1218.50	3.2066	1.45496	2.117
You are satisfied with the attitude and manner of delivering services by the staff of the university.	380	1	5	1314	3.46	1.422	2.022
You are willing to recommend the university to others because the Staff are friendly and have cordial relationship with the students.	380	1	5	1299	3.42	1.424	2.028
You are willing to recommend the university to others because the Staff deliver their lectures to the understanding of students.	380	1	5	1139	3.00	1.491	2.224
You are willing to recommend the university to others because lecturers are accessible and available to students for academic purposes.	380	1	5	1134	2.98	1.551	2.406
You are willing to recommend the university to others because Lecturers produce quiz and exam results promptly and accessible to students.	380	1	5	1231	3.24	1.467	2.151

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

You are willing to recommend the 380 1 5 1194 3.14 1.595 2.544 university to others because Staff do not exploit or demand for gratification before rendering their services.

Valid N (listwise) 380

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires' data 2021)

The data in (table 4.12) illustrate the summary of the statistics for the dimension of the predictor variable "Employee Engagement" with summarized values for central tendency as it relates students' referral based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that five (5) indicators in the scale had weighted mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00, while only one (1) indicator in the scale had weighted mean scores below the criterion mean of 3.00, based on 5-point likert scale which implied that the response is also moderate. With a grand mean of 3.20, the respondents agreed that the influence of employee engagement on students' referral in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.

4.2.3 Bivariate Analyses

The bivariate relationship determination in this section was done using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) in the assessment of the relationship between the dimensions of service delivery and students satisfaction. Thus, in determining the respective strength and statistical relationship of the association between these variables, the researchers were guided by the work of Cohen et al. (2007). The coefficient of correlation (effect size), the strength of association and statistically significant decision according to Cohen, et al. (2007) is interpreted below.

Table 4.13: Cohen et al statistical correlation decision scale frame

S/N	Statistical Significance	Association
i.	0.1 – 0.29	Very Weak
ii.	0.3 – 0.49	Weak
iii.	0.5 – 0.69	Moderate
iv.	0.70 – 0.79	Strong
v.	0.80 – 1.00	Very strong

Source: Cohen et al (2007)

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

Cohen et al (2007) posited that, effect size is an easy way to quantify both relationship and difference between two groups and at the same time to measure the effectiveness and statistical significance. Generally, the decision rule for the acceptance or rejection of hypothetical statements is premised on the adoption of a 0.05 significance threshold due to its 95% test on all hypotheses. Similarly, for the purpose of ease of presentation analysis and interpretation understanding, the researchers proposed hypotheses under the following:

1. Service culture and increased students' enrolment.
2. Service culture and students' referrals.
3. Service responsiveness and increased students' enrollment.
4. Service responsiveness and students' referrals.
5. Service quality and increased students' enrollment.
6. Service quality and students' referrals.
7. Employee engagement and increased students' enrollment.
8. Employee engagement and student's referral.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between service culture and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Table 4.14: Computation of relationship between service culture and increased students' enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Correlations		SERVICE CULTURE	INCREASED ENROLMENT	STUDENTS'
SERVICE CULTURE	Pearson Correlation	1	.739**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	380	380	
INCREASED STUDENTS' ENROLMENT	Pearson Correlation	.739**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	380	380	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS-generated Output

Table 4.14 shows a correlated result of an analysis on service culture and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja. The result indicates that service culture has a strong positive correlation with increased students enrolment ($r = .739$) which is significant at 0.05

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

level. Based on this result, hypothesis one (H_{01}) of no significant relationship between service culture and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja is rejected. Thus, there is a significant positive relationship between service culture and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between service culture and students referrals in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Table 4.15: Computation of relationship between service culture and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Correlations		STUDENTS REFERRAL	SERVICE CULTURE
STUDENTS REFERRAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.752**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	380	380
SERVICE CULTURE	Pearson Correlation	.752**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS-generated Output

Table 4.15 shows a correlated result of an analysis on service culture and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja. The result indicates that service culture has a strong positive correlation with students referral ($r = .752$) which is significant at 0.05 level. Based on this result, hypothesis two (H_{02}) of no significant relationship between service culture and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja is rejected. Thus, there is a significant positive relationship between service culture and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant relationship between service responsiveness and increased students enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Table 4.16: Computation of relationship between service responsiveness and increased students' enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Correlations		INCREASED STUDENTS' SERVICE	
		ENROLMENT	RESPONSIVENESS
INCREASED STUDENTS' ENROLMENT	Pearson Correlation	1	.275**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	380	380
SERVICE RESPONSIVENESS	Pearson Correlation	.275**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS-generated Output

Table 4.16 shows a correlated result of an analysis on service responsiveness and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja. The result indicates that service responsiveness has a very weak correlation ($r = .275$) with increased students' enrolment but significant at 0.05 level which indicates a positive relationship. Based on this result, hypothesis three (H_{03}) of no significant relationship between service responsiveness and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja is rejected. Thus, a very weak positive relationship exists between service responsiveness and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant relationship between service responsiveness and students referrals in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T. Abuja.

Table 4.17: Computation of relationship between service responsiveness and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Correlations		STUDENTS REFERRAL	SERVICE RESPONSIVENESS
STUDENTS REFERRAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.483**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	380	380
SERVICE RESPONSIVENESS	Pearson Correlation	.483**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS-generated Output

Table 4.17 shows a correlated result of an analysis on service responsiveness and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja. The result indicates that service responsiveness has a positive correlation with students' referral. However, the relationship is weak ($r = .483$) but significant at 0.05 level. Based on this result, hypothesis four (H_{04}) of no significant relationship between service responsiveness and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja is rejected. Hence, a weak positive relationship exists between service responsiveness and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Hypothesis 5

There is no significant relationship between service quality and increased students enrollment in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T. Abuja.

Table 4.18: Computation of relationship between service quality and increased students' enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Correlations		INCREASED ENROLMENT	STUDENTS'SERVICE QUALITY
INCREASED ENROLMENT	Pearson Correlation	1	.701**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	380	380
SERVICE QUALITY	Pearson Correlation	.701**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS-generated Output

Table 4.18 shows a correlated result of an analysis on service quality and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja. The result indicates that service quality has a strong positive correlation with increased students enrolment ($r = .701$) which is significant at 0.05 level. Based on this result, hypothesis three (H_{03}) of no significant relationship between service quality and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja is rejected. Thus, there is a significant positive relationship exists between service quality and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Hypothesis 6

There is no significant relationship between service quality and students referrals in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Table 4.19: Computation of relationship between service quality and student’s referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Correlations		STUDENTS	
		REFERRAL	SERVICE QUALITY
STUDENTS REFERRAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.713**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	380	380
SERVICE QUALITY	Pearson Correlation	.713**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS-generated Output

Table 4.18 shows a correlated result of an analysis on service quality and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja. The result indicates that service quality has a strong positive correlation with students referral ($r = .713$) which is significant at 0.05 level. Based on this result, hypothesis two (H_{06}) of no significant relationship between service quality and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja is rejected. Thus, there is a significant positive relationship between service quality and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Hypothesis 7

There is no significant relationship between employee engagement and increased students enrollment in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Table 4.20: Computation of relationship between employee engagement and increased students' enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Correlations		INCREASED ENROLMENT	STUDENTS'EMPLOYEE'S ENGAGEMENT
INCREASED ENROLMENT	Pearson Correlation	1	.784**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	380	380
EMPLOYEE'S ENGAGEMENT	Pearson Correlation	.784**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS-generated Output

Table 4.20 shows a correlated result of an analysis on employee engagement and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja. The result indicates that employee engagement has a strong positive correlation with increased students enrolment ($r = .784$) which is significant at 0.05 level. Based on this result, hypothesis seven (H_{07}) of no significant relationship between employee engagement and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja is rejected. Thus, there is a significant positive relationship between employee engagement and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Hypothesis 8

There is no significant relationship between employee engagement and students referral in privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Table 4.21: Computation of relationship between employee engagement and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja

Correlations		STUDENTS REFERRAL	EMPLOYEE'S ENGAGEMENT
STUDENTS REFERRAL	Pearson Correlation	1	.776**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	380	380
EMPLOYEE'S ENGAGEMENT	Pearson Correlation	.776**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS-generated Output

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

Table 4.21 shows a correlated result of an analysis on employee engagement and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja. The result indicates that employee engagement has a strong positive correlation with students referral ($r = .776$) which is significant at 0.05 level. Based on this result, hypothesis eight (H_{08}) of no significant relationship between employee engagement and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja is rejected. Thus, there is a significant positive relationship between employee engagement and students in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Summary of Findings

Based on the analysis of data and Hypotheses testing, the following findings were made:

- That the influence of service culture on increased students' enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.
- That the influence of service culture on students' referral in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.
- That the influence of service responsiveness on increased students' enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a low extent.
- That the influence of service responsiveness on students' referral in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a low extent.

- That the influence of service quality on increased students' enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.
- That the influence of service quality on students' referral in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.
- That the influence of employee engagement on increased students' enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.
- That the influence of employee engagement on students' referral in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja is to a moderate extent.
- Also, it was found that a strong positive significant relationship exist between service culture and increased students' enrolment in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja.
- A strong positive significant relationship exists between service culture and students' referral in privately-owned universities in F.C.T Abuja.
- A very weak positive relationship exists between service responsiveness and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.
- A weak positive relationship exists between service responsiveness and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

- A strong significant positive relationship exists between service quality and increased students enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.
- A strong significant positive relationship exists between service quality and students referral in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.
- Furthermore, a strong significant positive relationship exists between employee engagement and increased students' enrolment in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.
- Finally, a strong significant positive relationship also exists between employee engagement and students in Privately-owned Universities in F.C.T Abuja.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question one seeks to ascertain the extent of relationship between Service Culture and Students Satisfaction (measured in terms of increased student's enrollment and students referrals) in Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja. The result of the statistical analysis shows that the relationship is moderate, while the result of the hypotheses tested shows a significant positive relationship between the two variables. The reasons for this relationship is because three indicators of the sub-variables (Rules and Regulations of the Universities, Leadership style of the university, and Promotional activities of the Universities) have higher mean scores (frequencies) regarding the level of satisfaction derived from them by the

students than the other one indicator (procedures for obtaining the universities' services). The implication of this is that the students are less satisfied with the procedures for obtaining the universities' services. Hence, answer to Research Question one has been provided.

Research Question two seeks to ascertain the extent of relationship between Service Responsiveness and Students Satisfaction (measured in terms of increased student's enrollment and students referrals) in Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja. The result of the statistical analyses shows that the relationship is weak. This point is further buttressed by the result of the hypotheses testing which proves that there is a weak positive relationship between Service Responsiveness and students' satisfaction. This weak relationship is because only one indicator of the sub-variables (flexibility and willingness of the university to customize its services according to student's needs) has higher mean score (frequency) than other indicators of sub-variables (level attention given to students complaint, promptness in responding to students complaints, and constant contact with students to ascertain their level of satisfaction for possible amendments on their services). The implication of this is that the students are not satisfied with the level attention given to student's complaint, lack of promptness in responding to students' complaints, and lack of constant contact with students to ascertain their

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

level of satisfaction for possible amendments on their services. Hence, answer to Research Question two has been provided.

Research Question three seeks to ascertain the extent of relationship between Service Quality and Students Satisfaction (measured in terms of increased student's enrollment and students' referrals) in Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja. The result of the statistical analyses shows that the relationship is moderate. This point is further buttressed by the result of the hypotheses testing which proves that there is a significant positive relationship between Service Quality and students' satisfaction. This strong positive relationship is based on the fact that two indicators of the sub-variables such as Services Reliability and Staff Empathy have meaner than indicators of sub-variables such as availability of teaching aids, good learning environment Assurances by staff. The implication of this is that the students are not satisfied with the quality of teaching aids, learning environment and nature of assurances from staff. Hence, answer to Research Question three has been provided.

Research Question four seeks to ascertain the extent of relationship between Employee Engagement and Students Satisfaction (measured in terms of increased student's enrollment and students' referrals) in Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja. The result of the statistical analyses shows that the relationship is moderate. This point is further buttressed by the result of the hypotheses

testing which proves that there is a significant positive relationship between Employee Engagement and students' satisfaction. This strong positive relationship is based on the fact that five indicators of the sub-variables including attitude and manner of delivering services by staff, friendly and cordial relationship of staff with students, accessibility and availability of lecturers of lecturers to students for academic purposes, and lecturers releasing quiz and exam results promptly and making them accessible for students have high means (frequencies) more than indicators of sub-variables as lecturers delivering lecturers to the understanding of students. The implication of this is that the students are not satisfied with the manner with which lecturers deliver lectures. Hence, answer to Research Question four has been provided.

Conclusion

From the foregoing, the need for efficient and effective service delivery capabilities for attracting student's satisfaction by privately-owned universities in FCT Abuja is important. The population of FCT Abuja is increasing geometrically, the increasing need for university education in the territory and the country at large. But given the higher fees charged by privately-owned universities in FCT Abuja, and the licensing of more privately-owned universities in all parts of the country, privately-owned universities in FCT Abuja are faced with competition. The best option to win competition and achieve business growth is by achieving

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

students' satisfaction through superb Service Delivery Capabilities.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the study recommends as follows.

- (i) Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja should reduce and smoothen the length and procedures for delivering services to students.
- (ii) Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja should always give individual and serious attention to students' complaint.
- (iii) Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja should always promptly respond to students' complaints.
- (iv) Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja should always maintain constant contact with students so as to ascertain their level of satisfaction at all times.
- (v) Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja should always provide services according to the needs of students.
- (vi) Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja should utilize technologically-advanced teaching aids for delivering services to students in a good learning environment.
- (vii) Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja should utilize academic staff with adequate skills in areas of study and teaching, and capable of using technologically-advanced teaching aids to make students understand what they teach with needed assurance for quality services.

- (viii) Privately-owned Universities in FCT Abuja should provide good learning environment with steady internet access, electronic and physical library, recreation and sporting facilities, and adequate security of life and properties within the campus.

Contribution to Scholarship

Not much has been published on Service Delivery Capabilities tools for University Education or Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. The reason behind this may have been occasioned by the existing dominance and popularity of Government owned Universities and Tertiary Institutions. Also attributable to the present weak or lack of empirical study or existing literature in Service Delivery Capabilities tools for University Education or Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria is the visible lack of competitive orientation among the Managers of these Government-owned Universities and Tertiary Institutions. Presently there is an increasingly high need for university and higher education in Nigeria. This need has overwhelmed the current capacity of Universities and Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. To close this gap, more number of Privately-owned Universities and other Tertiary Institutions have been licensed by the National Universities Commission to establish and operate and they are operating. The increasing number of Privately-owned Universities in the country has created completion and further widens the competitive environment in the Privately-owned University Education

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

Environment in Nigeria. Since University Education is a Service with unique characteristics, there is the need to understand how to apply Service Delivery Tools in the Privately-owned Universities Business Environment in Nigeria and other developing countries. Therefore, how to apply the Service Delivery Tools by Privately-owned Universities in Nigeria and other developing countries is a contribution to knowledge and scholarship by this study.

Limitations of the Study

The major limitations of this study were getting access to the students in the various universities used for this study and convincing the students to fill the questionnaire. The Researcher took the pain to visit the universities with introductory letters. With the assistance of some lecturers who also showed interest on the topic of this study, the students were assessed while having lectures. Initially the students were skeptical over filling the questionnaire because they were afraid of expressing their opinion. But after explanation by the Researcher and the lecturers that accompanied the Researcher, the students filled the Questionnaire and returned immediately to the Researcher. Similar experience was received in all the universities.

Suggestion for further studies

It is suggested that further studies could be carried out with Privately-owned Universities in other parts of the country since this study was executed in FCT Abuja.

REFERENCES

- Aaker, D. A., Kumar, V., & Day, G. S. (1997). *Marketing Research* (6th ed.). John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Akagbue, B. A. (2016). Managing Academic Service Delivery in South-South Nigeria Universities for National Education Transformation. *International Journal of Education Practice*, 4(6).
- Akintayo, D. I. (2008). University Educational Service Delivery in a changing world: Implications for Ethical Values and Leadership Integrity in Nigeria. *Journal of College Teaching and Learning*.
- Akpan, C. P. (2014). Students' Perception of Teacher's Classroom Effectiveness of their Self-Concept in Lagos Metropolis. *African Higher Education Review (AHER)*, 8(2).
- Akpan, C. P. (2014, September). ICT Competence and Lecturers Job Efficacy: A Study of two Universities in Nigeria. *African Higher Education Review (AHER)*, 8(2).
- Ali, A. K. (2017). The Quality of Educational Services and its effect on Students Satisfaction: An Empirical Study on Students of Alrifacq Private University in

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

- Libya. *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective*, 6(1).
- Amadi, L. (2021). *Research Methodology and Statistical Analysis*. Peace Publishes Ltd.
- Amako, I., & Kasamoah, G. (2020). Indicators of Students Satisfaction of Quality Education Services in Some Selected Universities in Ghana. *South African Journal of Higher Education*.
- Bardiam, D. M. (1995). *Research Methods in Administrative Science (2nd ed.)*. Paragraphics.
- Bennett, D. G., & Wright, T. A. (2014). Cronbach's Alpha Reliability: Interval estimation, Hypothesis Testing, and Sample Size Planning. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*.
- Berry, L. L., & Parasuraman, A. (1991). *Marketing Services: Competing through Quality*. The Free Press.
- Billups, F. D. (2020). *Measuring College Students Satisfaction: A Multi-year Study of the Factors Leading to Persistence*. Scholars Archive@JWU Online.
- Blythe, J. (2003). *Marketing Strategy*. McGraw Hill Education.
- Brassington, F., & Pettitt, S. (2006). *Principles of Marketing (4th ed.)*. Prentice Hall Inc.
- Burns, A. C., & Bush, R. F. (1995). *Marketing Research*. Practice Hall, Inc.
- Copley, L. (2017). 6 Reasons why customers' Satisfaction is important. *The call-takers Online*.
- Cravens, D. W., & Piercy, N. F. (2003). *Strategic Marketing (7th ed.)*. McGraw Hill.
- Daniel, D., Liben, G., & Adugna, A. (2017). Assessment of Students Satisfaction: A Study of Dire Dawa University, Ethiopia. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(4).
- Ekpoh, U. I. (2018). Assessing University Students Satisfaction with Service Delivery: Implication for Educational Management. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Science - The Academia*.
- Garnjost, P., & Lawter, L. (2019). Undergraduates Satisfaction and Perception of Learning outcomes across Teacher- and Learner-Focused Pedagogies. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 17(18).
- Gliem, J. A., & Gliem, R. R. (2003). Calculating, Interpreting, Reporting Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient for Likert-Type Scales. *Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference in Adult, Continuing and Community Education*.

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

- Hair, J. F., Bush, R. P., & Ortinau, D. J. (2003). *Marketing Research within a changing information environment* (2nd ed.). McGraw Hill Irwin.
- Hagen, S., Vignali, C., & Kaufmann, H. R. (2006). A Student Satisfaction Model for Austrian Higher Education Providers considering aspects of Marketing Communications. *Journal of Innovative Marketing Online*.
- Hawkins, D. I., Best, R. J., & Coney, K. A. (2001). *Consumer Behavior: Building Marketing Strategy* (8th ed.). McGraw Hill Irwin.
- Hoque, K. E., Razak, A. Z., & Zohora, M. F. (2013). Service Delivery in Higher Education (HE): A Comparative study between Public and Private Universities. *Research gate - Life Science Journal*, 10(3), 108-117.
- Ibrahim, A. W. (2014). The Students' Perception of Teacher's Classroom Effectiveness of their Self-concept in Lagos Metropolis. *Journal of Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Jobber, D. (2004). *Principles and Practice of Marketing* (4th ed.). McGraw Hill Irwin.
- Kerin, R. A., Berkowitz, E. N., Hartley, S. W., & Rudelus, W. (2003). *Marketing* (7th ed.). McGraw Hill Irwin.
- Kim, B. J., Koichiro, O., & Cho, J. (2013). Customer Satisfaction Theory in Public Administration Education: Revisiting Students Evaluation of Teaching. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 36(11).
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2006). *Marketing Management* (12th ed.). Person Education.
- Kulthum, N., Mukwanda, M., & Kyaligonsa, R. (2019). Professional Development Practice and Service Delivery of Academic Staff at Kampala International University and Kyambogo University. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*.
- Lussier, R. N. (2006). *Management Fundamentals: Concepts, Applications and Skill Development*. Thomson-South Western.
- Madura, J. (2004a). *Introduction to Business* (3rd ed.). Thomson-South Western.
- Madura, J. (2004b). *Introduction to Business* (3rd ed.). Australia: Thomson-South Western.

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

- Manzoor, H. (2013). Measuring Students Satisfaction in Public and Private Universities in Pakistan. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research Interdisciplinary*, 13(3).
- Nnamka, C. V. (2014). Improving Access to University Education: The Case of the National Open University of Nigeria. *African Higher Education Review (AHER)*, 8(2).
- Ovat, O. (2019). Quality Service Delivery and Students Satisfaction in Public Universities in South-Eastern Nigeria. *Research Gate for IJEAST*.
- Olawure, O. P., & Ajayi, T. B. (2017). Emergence of Private Universities in Nigeria and various challenges. *Journal of Lagos State Polytechnic, Ikorodu Lagos*.
- Osuji, C., Marafa, R. M., & Beekey, C. (2016). A Case of Private Sector Participation in Higher Education Development in Africa with specific reference to recovery in Globalized Economy. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 8(1).
- Palmer, A. (2005). *Principles of Services Marketing* (14th ed.). The McGraw-Hill Companies.
- Reader, C. (2017). *Theory of Human Service Delivery, Business Operations, Biz Fluent Online*.
- Salles, F. L. P. (2019). Evaluation of Satisfaction of Undergraduate Students through Structural Equation Modeling. *Journal of Education*.
- Sharma, D. D. (2010). *Marketing Research: Principles, Applications and Cases*. Sultan Chand & Sons.
- Stephens, P. (2014). Undergraduate Students' Satisfaction: Investigating the Measurement, Dimensionality, and Nature of the Construct using the Rasch Model. *University of Kentucky, Uknowledge*.
- Teya, E. M. (2019). Students' Perception of Service Delivery in the University of Nairobi: A study of Kisii Extra-Mural Centre. *University of Nairobi Kenya Research Archive*.
- Ugbuozobe, J. E. M., & Okeke, E. P. (2014). Appraisal of the Availability and Utilization of Information and Communication Technology in the Higher Education System. *African Higher Education Review*, 6(2).
- Walter, O. C., Boyd, H. W., Mullins, J., & Larreche, J. (2003). *Marketing Strategy*:

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi

Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development

Adv. J. Bus. Ent. Dev.

Volume: 7; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2023

ISSN: 4405-3914 (Print Version)

ISSN: 2507-4309 (Electronic Version)

Impact Factor: 4.03

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajbed/index.php/ajbed>

A Decision-Focused Approach (4th ed.).
McGraw Hill Irwin.

Wohlstetter, P. M., Courtney, L., Hentschke, G. C., & Smith, J. (2004). Improving Service Delivery in Education through collaboration: An exploratory

Weerasinghe, I. M. S., Lalitha, R. M., & Fernando, S. (2017). Students Satisfaction in Higher Education: A Literature Review. *American Journal of Education Research*, 5(5).

Zeithaml, V.A. & Bitner, M.J., (200). *Services Marketing: Integrating Customer Focus Across Firm*, 2nd-ed. Irwin McGraw Hill

APPENDIX RELIABILITY STATISTICS

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Indicators
.967	5	Service Culture And Increase Students' Enrollment
.969	5	Service Culture And Students' Referral
.985	5	Service Quality And Increase Students' Enrollment
.985	5	Service Quality And Students' Referral
.985	5	Service Responsiveness And Increase Students' Enrollment
.984	5	Service Responsiveness And Students' Referral
.987	5	Employee's Engagement And Increase Students' Enrollment
.989	6	Employee's Engagement And Students' Referral
.998	41	

Dr. Jude E. Madu and Dr. Lawrence Amadi